

Interactive Image Descriptions

In Digital/Audio Books for Individuals with Visual Impairments

Alt Text: A person seated in a library with warm light holds a tablet displaying an open book, wearing headphones to indicate screen reader use. Wooden bookshelves blur in the background. The image is AI generated

Internship Project: 26-08-2024 to 17-01-2025

Pranav Prasun
MSc Design for Interaction
Delft University of Technology

Project done with Koninklijke Bibliotheek, The Hague

Alt Text: Icon for CC BY SA.
Horizontally, CC in a circle, a standing human figure in a circle, and a circular arrow for sharing in a circle)

This project was undertaken by Pranav Prasun, MSc Design for Interaction (Industrial Design Engineering, TU Delft), under the supervision of Ted van der Togt (Researcher, Koninklijke Bibliotheek, The Hague) and Dr. Jeff Love (Assistant Professor and Data Steward, Industrial Design Engineering, TU Delft). The project was conducted as part of an internship at KB (Koninklijke Bibliotheek) from August 2024 to January 2025.

Contact: pranavprasun.com/contact

REPORT

CONTENT

Report

Content

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	5
1. INTRODUCTION	6
2. RESEARCH PROBLEM	7
3. METHOD/APPROACH	9
4. ONLINE SURVEY:	10
5. GENERATIVE SESSION	12
6. DESIGN GOAL	14
7. INTERACTION VISION	15
8. PROTOTYPING AND PRE-TESTING	16
9. USER TEST	19
10. LIMITATIONS OF RESULTS	20
11. REFLECTIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS	21

Appendix

References

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Individuals with visual impairments face significant challenges accessing visual information in books, particularly digital formats like e-books and audiobooks. Visual details are essential for understanding narratives and contexts, yet their accessibility remains insufficient. As mentioned in the article “The Accessible Books Consortium: what it means for publishers” by Catherine Jewell in WIPO magazine in 2018, globally, less than 10% of published works are available in accessible formats, leaving a significant gap in inclusive for people with visual impairments. This project investigates how artificial intelligence (AI) and interactive technologies can bridge this gap.

Research Problem

Existing image descriptions often lack context or detail and fail to meet the diverse needs of users. Preferences vary widely based on factors such as the type and onset of visual impairment, age, and personal interests (further elaborated in the chapters ahead). A one-size-fits-all approach to image descriptions is inadequate, highlighting the need for customizable, context-aware solutions.

Methodological Approach

A mixed-methods approach was employed, including desk research, user interviews, surveys, generative co-creation sessions, and prototype testing. A survey of twelve participants revealed differences in user preferences based on their age and the onset of their visual impairment. Younger users preferred detailed, customizable descriptions, while older users were more neutral about personalization. Co-creation sessions further emphasized the importance of integrating descriptions seamlessly into the reading experience.

Proposed Solutions

The research explored AI-driven, interactive solutions to enhance image accessibility without disrupting the

reading flow. Key proposals included:

Haptic Feedback: Subtle vibrations alert users to an image, with optional prompts for additional details.
Voice-Activated Interaction: Users can ask specific questions about an image, such as “Describe the setting” or “What are the people wearing?”
AI-Driven Personalization: Customizable descriptions tailored to user preferences and book context, adjustable in depth and length.

Findings and Key Insights

Prototype testing highlighted a strong user preference for simple and flexible solutions. Participants valued the ability to control the level of detail in image descriptions, allowing uninterrupted reading. Privacy concerns associated with AI use emerged as a notable issue. The usability assessment, using the System Usability Scale (SUS), yielded an average score of 80, indicating excellent usability. However, the small sample size underscores the need for further validation.

Future Directions

This research identifies the potential for context-aware, interactive descriptions, emphasizing simplicity, flexibility, and privacy. Future work could explore integration into e-readers, mobile apps, or everyday portable devices. Key development areas include customizable image descriptions and the incorporation of context-aware AI functionalities.

Conclusion

This study highlights the critical need to improve the accessibility of visual content in books for individuals with visual impairments. Leveraging AI, haptic technologies, and user-centered design principles can create a more inclusive and engaging reading experience. The research lays a good foundation for further exploration and broader validation.

1. Introduction

Visuals in books play a vital role in enriching narratives, providing context, and enhancing the reading experience. However, for readers with visual impairments, these elements often remain inaccessible due to inadequate or absent image descriptions. According to the article “The Accessible Books Consortium: What It Means for Publishers” by Catherine Jewell, published in WIPO Magazine in 2018, less than 10% of published works globally are available in accessible formats. This significant gap highlights the challenges faced by individuals with visual impairments in accessing inclusive content.

At the outset of this internship, I focused on exploring ways to empathize with visually impaired users, employing “empathy” as a design-thinking tool to understand their perspectives and challenges. One of the initial exercises involved using a 3D-printed tactile image sourced from the Internet. With my eyes closed, I attempted to recreate the image in my mind by moving my fingers over its surface. The difficulty of interpreting tactile details underscored the challenges faced by visually impaired users in accessing visual information, as well as their dexterity.

A conversation with Tessa, the Accessibility and Adapted Reading Coordinator at KB, provided further context. Tessa had shared resources to help me experience braille (including example shown in the image below). The conversation (*abridged*) was like:

P: Thank you for the braille books. I’ve looked through them. I find it difficult to recognize tactile images and retain details after a short time. It seems to require

significant skill to mentally compile all the details into a coherent picture.

T: Exactly! It’s really challenging. Imagine how hard it must be for someone who has never had vision to interpret such tactile lines into a meaningful picture. The more you interact with visually impaired individuals, the more questions arise about how they perceive the world, and the deeper my admiration grows for how they navigate and operate within it.

This conversation left deep my admiration for people with visual impairments. Another such conversation was with Ted, my project supervisor, who has experience of working in accessibility for over a decade: *each individual has unique backgrounds, interests, and information needs. As such, a single type of image description might not suffice for all readers. Meanwhile, creating multiple versions of image descriptions might not be feasible for publishers, as it would require a significant amount of manual effort.*

To address this issue, I explored solutions involving AI and interactive technologies to make visuals in digital books more accessible and tested the idea in ‘Wizard of Oz’ style. The internship followed a structured process encompassing desk research, surveys, interviews, generative sessions, prototyping, and user testing. These activities culminated in a final presentation of findings to KB’s research team.

This report documents the journey and insights derived from 432 hours of research and design work.

Alt Text: Image of a Tactile Line Drawing: Zoomed in view of Mona Lisa in raised line drawing style and shadows represented as raised dot which makes the overall picture tactile.

2. Research Problem

Despite the growing focus on digital accessibility, readers with visual impairment face significant barriers when accessing images in books. Common issues include:

- **Lack of Adequate Descriptions:** Existing descriptions often fail to provide sufficient detail or context.
- **Diverse User Needs:** Preferences vary significantly based on age, onset of visual impairment, and technological familiarity.
- **Complex Visuals:** Charts, graphs, and intricate illustrations

pose unique challenges for accessibility tools. For example, the comic strip as shown below usually has text as part of the image which is not accessible by the screen reader and thus is completely skipped by it.

The project hypothesized that a one-size-fits-all approach to image descriptions is inadequate. Instead, personalized, context-aware, and adaptable solutions are necessary to address the diverse requirements of visually impaired readers.

Alt text: Black and White Comic Strip with 3 panels: Left side full panel - A lone figure (man) walks down a narrow cobblestone street lined with crumbling buildings under a moonlit sky and text reading ‘His footsteps echoed, swallowed by the silent, eerie street.’ Top right panel shows a half open inside view of the old castle that exposes the night sky and stars in the background, and reads- ‘The staircase going down into darkness, and suddenly a faint whimpering sound catches attention’. And lastly bottom right panel has a close up view with walls and sky partly visible and it reads, ‘There was a flickering glow pulsing like a heartbeat.. visible through the old broken part of the giant castle window.’

3. Method and Desk Research

This study adopted a structured, iterative approach, which included:

1. Desk Research: Exploring existing literature, tools, and practices related to image accessibility.
2. Online Surveys: Gathering insights on user preferences and challenges.
3. User & Expert Interviews: Engaging with visually impaired readers and experts for nuanced understanding.
4. Generative Sessions: Facilitating co-creation activities to ideate solutions.
5. Prototype Testing: Evaluating AI-driven, interactive image description tools through user feedback.

This mixed-method approach ensured a comprehensive understanding of the problem space and informed user-centered design solutions.

Desk Research:
The desk research explored current trends, technologies, and practices in making visual content accessible for visually impaired individuals. Key areas of investigation included AI tools for image descriptions, crowd-sourcing platforms, inclusive publishing

practices, and co-design methodologies for accessibility. Existing tools like Microsoft's Caption Bot, Google's Show & Tell, and platforms like BeMyEyes were analyzed for functions and more. Literature such as Books Without Barriers and Pragmatic Factors in [Automatic] Image Description provided insights into the challenges and best practices in automated and manual image descriptions. Co-design approaches emphasized the importance of involving users who are blind or visually impaired in the creation of solutions.

The research also highlighted challenges with existing systems, including biases in AI-generated descriptions, the difficulty of interpreting tactile representations, and the need for intuitive voice-based interactions. Additionally, inclusive publishing guidelines outlined steps to make content accessible for diverse user groups. Stakeholders identified include libraries, accessibility organizations, publishers, and software/hardware companies, reflecting the collaborative nature required for developing effective solutions.

A. Preparation for the Session

Desk Research

Expert Interview

Online Survey

Alt Text: Three line drawings representing different research methods: On the left, below the text 'Desk Research,' a top-view illustration shows a desktop setup with a keyboard, mouse, and a hand holding a cup of coffee. In the center, below the text 'Expert Interview,' an illustration depicts a video call with a person visible on a desktop monitor. On the right, below the text 'Online Survey,' an illustration shows several raised hands, symbolizing agreement or participation."

B. In the week prior to the Generative Session Day (As individual Participant)

Reading and Sharing the Thoughts [DO + SAY]

Interview [SAY]

Alt Text: Two line drawings showing research activities before the Generative Session: Left, below 'Reading and Sharing the Thoughts [Do and Say]': An open book with icons and photos emerging, symbolizing visuals in a book. Right, below 'Interview [Say]': A phone and a desktop during a video call. The visuals together show that participants prepare by reading a book with visuals and sharing their experience, followed by an interview.

C. On the Generative Session Day (For Group Participation)

Experience Sharing [SAY]

Participants share their reading experiences of books 'with images'. Anyone can share, pitch in, reflect on the idea, or build upon each other's experience to deepen on the issues.

Wizard of Oz with CustomGPT [DO]

An interactive prototype using this custom GPT (that tells about an image in 30 words. And then from ChatGPT phone app, a user can also go on a voice call to ask more questions. Calling this as 'wizard of oz' as we intend the users to experience that there is an actual prototype that works, but in fact we manually need to make photos and start the call etc. This is the temporary link of the custom made GPT: <https://chatgpt.com/g/g-00sFFSvF2-image-narrator>. (GPT Instructions in Appendix)

Co-Creation [MAKE]

The participants are given a situation in future considering the rise of technology, AI and other resources. If there is no limit on the possibilities, 'How might be the ideal way to know about images in a book'.

Some tinkering materials like vecro, magnetic pads, clay etc are available to use in this if anyone wishes to use. These materials can be something to fidget with or imagine but are not necessary to use for this part.

Alt Text: Above is the overview of the plan for Generative session day. There are three line drawings representing 3 parts of the session. First on the left is a heading text 'Experience Sharing [Say]' below which is the illustration of some people talking to each other with the speech bubble over them showing the first part is sharing session about reading experience. Second Image in the center is the heading text 'Wizard of Oz with CustomGPT' and the illustration below shows a phone and an dummy profile of a human with multiple text bubbles showing an interaction with the AI agent in the phone. And the last on the right below the text 'Co-Creation[MAKE]' shows an illustration of three people in their nice comfortable zone sitting on bean bags while talking and working together. This represents the last part of the session which is co-creation.

4. Online Survey

The online survey sought to uncover the challenges faced by visually impaired readers and their preferences for image descriptions. Key insights included:

- 45% of the respondents agree that getting details about images are important for enjoying the book.
- 54% of the respondents would not skip any image-related information - highlighting a need for making images accessible
- Customization is Critical: 64% of respondents preferred tailored image descriptions.
- Challenges with Current Solutions: 82% expressed either skepticism or dissatisfaction about the effectiveness of existing descriptions.
- Age-Based Preferences: Younger users sought detailed descriptions, while older participants displayed varied opinions.

The received responses were also analysed on two basis, first being the onset of visual impairment. and second being the the age group of the respondents. Those who lost their vision later in life had a different response compared to those who experienced so early in their lives. Below are the insights

from the perspective of when they experienced loss of vision:

- Those who lost their vision early in their childhood or blind since birth valued image details but feel unsure about the descriptions.
- Those who lost their vision later in life, don't feel the descriptions are effective enough and are more inclined towards customisable image description.

And based on the age group of respondents, there were following insights:

- The younger age group are more inclined towards knowing image details, and want customisation however are quite skeptical if the details are good enough.
- The older age group have very differing opinions on image details and description quality and are not very keen on customised description.

These findings highlighted the need for adaptable solutions and laid the groundwork for subsequent research phases.

Extracts from Survey Responses

7. Getting details from the images is very important to me for enjoying/getting information from a book.(Rate on the scale of '1. Completely disagree' to '5. Completely agree'.)

Completely disagree	3
Somewhat Disagree	0
Neither agree nor disagree	3
Somewhat agree	5
Completely agree	0

Alt Text: A doughnut chart displaying responses on the importance of getting details about an image: 45% 'Somewhat Agree' which is maximum, then 27% each 'Completely Agree', and 'Neither Agree nor Disagree'. No responses for 'Somewhat Disagree' or 'Completely Disagree'.

8. I would prefer to skip any information about images in a book.(Rate on the scale of '1. Completely disagree' to '5. Completely agree'.)

Completely disagree	3
Somewhat Disagree	3
Neither agree nor disagree	4
Somewhat agree	1
Completely agree	0

Alt Text: A doughnut chart displaying responses on willingness to skip information about an image: 36% 'Neither Agrees nor Disagrees' which is maximum, then 27% 'Completely Disagree as well as Somewhat Disagree', and lowest 9% for 'Somewhat agree' and no one selected completely agree.

9. How effectively do currently available image descriptions or captions convey the content of images to you?

Very ineffectively	1
Somewhat ineffectively	2
Neither effectively nor ineffectively	6
Somewhat effectively	2
Very effectively	0

Alt Text: A doughnut chart displaying responses on effectiveness of current image description: 55% which is maximum find it 'Neither effective nor ineffective', then 18% find 'Somewhat ineffective and Somewhat Effective', and lowest 9% find it 'Very ineffective'. No one finds is very effective.

10. Would you like the option to customize the level of detail in image descriptions?

Yes	7
No	4
Other	0

Alt Text: A doughnut chart displaying responses on having an option to customise the level of detail in image description. 64% say they would want it. And 36% say they don't want it. All of these responses have been more categorically analysed in the main text.

5. Generative Session

The generative session held at KB emphasized user participation and creativity. Preparation included pre-session tasks such as reading image descriptions and sharing reflections. The session itself involved:

1. Experience Sharing: Participants discussed their experiences and frustrations with current image descriptions. Since there was an exercise before this session where they needed to go through a book with a few images, that helped the participants to have a fresh experience to build on during this activity (reference appendix)
2. Prototype Testing (Wizard of Oz): While hearing an audio book, a simulated AI system provided customizable descriptions, allowing participants to request additional details through voice commands.
3. Co-Creation: Participants brainstormed and ideal solutions using tactile and visual aids.

The session revealed a strong user preference for flexible, context-aware solutions that integrate seamlessly with existing systems. The session also highlighted several critical insights:

- Descriptions often reference images but lack sufficient detail or fail to connect to

other sections of the content.

- Text within images is inaccessible or difficult to interpret, and screen readers frequently overlook images entirely.
- Missing context in descriptions creates significant challenges for users.
- Human biases and AI misinterpretations can negatively affect the accuracy and usefulness of image descriptions.
- Users often rely on quick descriptions from other people rather than on AI or technological solutions for clarity.
- Effective descriptions should focus on the most attention-grabbing elements to convey essential information.
- While AI assistance can be beneficial, it must integrate seamlessly into the reading experience to be truly effective.
- Accessibility users find it particularly difficult to interpret tabular data and pie charts, underscoring the need for specialized solutions.
- These findings emphasize the importance of user-centered design and the need for solutions that prioritize accessibility and usability in diverse contexts.

Alt Text: Generative session setup with a table featuring a laptop, tactile prototypes, materials for interaction, books, snacks, and notes arranged for participant activities.

6. Design Goal

Based on the insights so far, the specified context was as below:

1. Users: People with visual impairment who read regularly (ebook or audio books)
2. Device: Own Device or in a library
3. Format: Digital books or audio books

Furthermore based on the insights on needs, the readers should be able to justify their following needs:

- a. Know about images as per individual preferences
- b. Should go well with the flow of reading and interaction should not take too long

- c. Context and focus in an image is important to know
- d. Avoid biases and misinterpretation
- e. As Plus (if feasible to include in the initial design iterations): Possibility to experience the world in the image

The project aimed to enable visually impaired readers to access and enjoy visual content effortlessly, without disrupting their reading flow.

Finally, a design goal specified below was concluded in this stage.

Alt Text: Design Goal stating, I want to enable enjoyable/effortless reading for people who are visually impaired and read books (digital/audio) by making the reading experience personalised and engaging, without losing their focus from the primary reading material (without breaking the flow).

Enable enjoyable/effortless reading is highlighted in yellow and is indicated as a possible product, service, environment or any combination of these. People who are visually impaired and read books is indicated as the target users and are highlighted in blue. And making reading experience personalised and engaging is marked as the intended effect and is highlighted in light purple.

7. Interaction Vision

In order to evaluate the design later if the desired interaction quality is achieved, the analogy of Interaction Vision was used.

The expected characters of interactions were: Intended characters of interaction:

- Be a part of an activity that people are familiar with.
- Reveals details not known initially
- Is present but does not attract too much attention

- Engaging, not too technical
- Very intuitive to do, or easy to learn after one trail

Inspired by the analogy of a guided gallery tour, the interaction vision emphasized:

- Layered, context-aware insights tailored to individual preferences.
- An intuitive interface that complements rather than interrupts the reading experience.

Alt Text: Two people in an art gallery, one is a curious visitor looking keenly at paintings and another formally dressed person as a friendly curator standing beside to guide when needed.

Interaction Vision:
The interaction with my concept should feel like touring a gallery with a friendly curator

8. Prototyping and Pre-Testing

Prototypes explored features such as:

- Haptic Feedback: Indicating the presence of images through vibrations.
- Voice Commands: Allowing users to request specific details, such as “What is the person wearing?” or “Describe the setting.”

Pre-tests informed iterative refinements, particularly in simplifying descriptions and addressing complex visuals like graphs.

First, a customised GPT was created and optimised based on multiple trials and refinements. The

GPT analyses any uploaded image and finally comes up with a short (less than 30 words) description about the image. It also offers the option to continue further with any more questions using voice chat function.

Next was making the haptic feedback system using simple itsy-bitsy kit. This lo-fi prototype was tested to be sure it gives the intended impression of the imagined automated system that gives subtle haptic and buzzer feedbacks (each separate) to notify an image along with a voice based interaction to learn more about the image, in case the reader wishes to.

Alt Text: Two screenshots of an app interface: The left screen displays an 'Image Narrator' a customised GPT, showing a photo of a modern office with a red backpack, a booklet on brain anatomy, and a potted palm near a partition wall, accompanied by descriptive text as a response generated by AI. Whiteboards and notes are visible in the background. The right screen shows a circular abstract image resembling a blue sky or clouds, with microphone and close buttons below. The page that open when continuing with voice based interaction with the GPT”

Alt Text: Desk setup with a laptop displaying 'The Girl with a Pearl Earring,' connected to an itsy-bitsy kit prototype for testing haptic and buzzer feedbacks. Notes, wires, and sensors are visible, representing a lo-fi system for image notifications and voice interaction.

Alt Text: A person testing a lo-fi foam ring with an actuator for vibrating image notifications during a prototype session, with a laptop and notes on the desk. An arrow from the itsy-bitsy kit connect to the detail view showing the vibration motor attached to the edge of a foam. Not visible in picture: Foam has a small hole to slide in a finger and feel the subtle vibrations.

9. User Test

The user test evaluated the prototypes' usability and effectiveness:

- Setup: Participants interacted with five curated images using haptic/ buzzer feedback along with AI-assisted descriptions. In first type of test, they interacted with an audio book and when there was an image in the narration, they got a haptic feedback. In the second, they got a buzzer feedback. In both of them there was the option to either continue with further voice based interaction or ignore the subtle haptics/buzz cues.
- Insights:
 - » Users appreciated the idea of a vibration to indicate images but emphasized the need for flexibility (e.g., the option to turn it off for long books).

- » Users liked the concept of tapping or using voice commands to request more information about an image (e.g., "Describe the person" or "What are they wearing?").
- » Privacy concerns emerged as a key consideration.

For a quantitative results, SUS analysis method was used. An average System Usability Scale (SUS) score of 80 indicated excellent usability. Some key points noted in the responses were:

- Key Points:
- Users appreciated the simplicity and integration of the system.
 - Areas for improvement include reducing perceived complexity and ensuring features don't feel cumbersome.

10. Limitations of Results

The study faced several limitations:

- **Small Sample Size:** Only two participants were involved generative session and two in testing, restricting the generalizability of findings. In total, the responses are from 4 participants.
- The survey was conducted online over a three-week period, gathering 12 responses from residents of the Netherlands and Belgium. The survey link was shared within relevant groups in these regions and thus has limitations.
- **Simulated Setup:** The Wizard of Oz prototype, while useful, lacked the realism of a fully functional system.
- **Limited Representation:** The study did not capture the perspectives of a broader demographic range. Also, the participants primarily preferred reading books using on screen readers or audio books. So the responses does not include those who read braille.

11. Reflections and Recommendations

Key reflections include:

- **Time Considerations:** Ethical approvals and user onboarding required more time than anticipated.
- **Need for Larger Validation:** Broader participant representation is essential for conclusive insights.
- **Use of AI** also comes with privacy concerns and thus ethical considerations for the users. There is also a concern for copyright issues for published materials with a use of non-localised AI.

Recommendations include:

- Interactive options, and context-aware

descriptions emerged as promising avenues.

- More refined prototypes with focus on identifying ways to incorporate such solution that integrates seamlessly in the everyday life of users.
- Personalized AI that supports image description (respecting user privacy) could be a promising area to explore.
- Refining prototypes to handle complex visuals more effectively.
- Allowing sufficient time for preparatory activities, such as HREC approvals, and onboarding enough participants for the research and test.

REFERENCES

1. Sanders, E., & Stappers, P. (2013). Convivial Toolbox: generative research for the front end of design.
2. Greene, S., Marchionini, G., Plaisant, C., & Shneiderman, B. (2000). Previews and overviews in digital libraries: Designing surrogates to support visual information seeking. *Journal of the American Society for Information Science*, 51(4), 380. [https://doi.org/10.1002/\(sici\)1097-4571\(2000\)51:4](https://doi.org/10.1002/(sici)1097-4571(2000)51:4)
3. Books without barriers. (n.d.). <https://publishers.asn.au/BooksWithoutBarriers>
4. Huang, H., & Liem, C. C. S. (2022). Social Inclusion in Curated Contexts: Insights from Museum Practices. 2022 ACM Conference on Fairness, Accountability, and Transparency, 300–309. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3531146.3533095>
5. Johnson, K. (2023, July 5). AI could change how blind people see the world. WIRED. <https://www.wired.com/story/ai-gpt4-could-change-how-blind-people-see-the-world/>
6. Robin, N. B. (2018). Facilitating discussion and shared meaning Rethinking co-design sessions with people with vision impairments. *ACM Proceedings*, 258–262. https://jglobal.jst.go.jp/en/detail?JGLOBAL_ID=202002232581513539
7. Van Miltenburg, C. (2019). Pragmatic factors in (automatic) image description. Emiel Van Miltenburg - Pragmatic Factors in [Automatic] Image Description. <https://research.tilburguniversity.edu/en/publications/pragmatic-factors-in-automatic-image-description>

